

HORIZON 2020 - Coordination and Support Action

Grant Agreement No: 101003766

**EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area**

Deliverable No. 1.5

**1st Summary and recording of thematic webinars
dedicated to improving European cooperation**

Submission of Deliverable

Document information	
Work Package	WP 1 Research Coordination
Deliverable No	D1.5
Deliverable title	1st Summary and recording of thematic webinars dedicated to improving European cooperation
Version	[Final]
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP - Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	IGOT-UL
Contributors	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – MICINN, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – UOULU, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – ISP-CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – RCN, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 6 – EPB, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - NWO, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – DAFSHE, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – UoS-CPS, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – BAI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 – UNIVIE, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 –IG-TUT, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – WOC Europe, <input type="checkbox"/> 15 – BELSPO, <input type="checkbox"/> 16 – AMAP, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 17 – IGOT UL, <input type="checkbox"/> 18 - SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 19 – UKRI-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 20 – ITU, <input type="checkbox"/> 21 – USB, <input type="checkbox"/> 22 – RANNIS, <input type="checkbox"/> 23 – FAMRI, <input type="checkbox"/> 24 – ICR, <input type="checkbox"/> 25 – SPI
Coordinating author	Gonçalo Vieira
Contributing authors	Joana Baptista, Joseph Nolan, Renuka Badhe
Due date	31 March 2022
Delivery date	07 April 2022

Document history	
Creation Date	January 2022
Revision	V1
Revision Date	06.04.2022
Author	IGOT-UL, AWI
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP lead approved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coordinator approved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Executive Board approved
Status date	06.04.2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003766

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY	4
1 Introduction	5
2 Thematic webinars dedicated to improving European cooperation	6
2.1 “Impact of COVID-19 on members of the EU Polar Cluster” webinar (15 January 2021)	6
2.2 “European Perspectives on the Arctic Science Ministerial Process” webinar (28 April 2021) ..	8
2.3 All-Atlantic “Networking from pole to pole: facilitating access for research and infrastructures” webinar (2 June 2021)	11
2.4 “How to apply for an EU PolarNet 2 Service Contract” webinar (7 July 2021)	13
2.5 COP26 Side event: “Polar warming, global warning” (3 November 2021)	14
2.6 “The new EU Arctic Policy and Research and Innovation” webinar (24 November 2021)	16

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Thematic webinars are one of the key communication formats within the strategy of EU-PolarNet 2 to foster cooperation at the European level. In 2021 the EU-PolarNet 2 organized six webinars, most in collaboration with the European Polar Board and the EU Polar Cluster. In order to increase visibility and impact, several webinars were presented in association to large events where different European and international stakeholders participated. These were the cases of the Arctic Science Ministerial 3 (April 2021), the All-Atlantic Conference 2022 (June 2021) and the UN COP26 (November 2021). The launch of the new EU Arctic Policy in 2021 provided an excellent framework to discuss the opportunities and needs for Arctic research and cooperation (November 2021). With the launch of the EU-PolarNet 2 call for service contracts, a novel contribution of the project, a webinar was also prepared for explaining the objectives and the application procedures (July 2021). With an internal focus on EU Polar Cluster projects, the impacts of COVID-19 on the members has been discussed, allowing to share best practices and to identify priority needs. The public webinars are available online, with links provided in the report.

1 Introduction

Thematic webinars are one of the key communication formats within the strategy of EU-PolarNet 2 to foster cooperation at the European level. This strategy had been prepared in pre-pandemic times, but with the situation that developed since March 2020 and that prevails still in early 2022, the webinar format became part of the work-life of scientists, policy-makers, stakeholders and the general public. The format is now widely accepted as a way to increase the dissemination of knowledge, to promote collaboration, while also to reduce the carbon footprint associated to international travelling. The EU-PolarNet 2 webinars benefited from this “new normal” framework, but with the impact of COVID-19 health measures, especially the lock-downs and travel restrictions, it is also true that a “screen-fatigue” started to affect a large number of stakeholders towards the mid of 2021. It is hence very important to find a good balance and to adjust the webinar offer, to best-fit the increasingly complex arena of webinars that are permanently occurring.

In 2021 the EU-PolarNet 2 organized six webinars, most in collaboration with the European Polar Board and the EU Polar Cluster. In order to increase visibility and impact, several webinars were presented associated to large events where different European and international stakeholders participated. These were the cases of the Arctic Science Ministerial 3 (April 2021), the All-Atlantic Conference 2022 (June 2021) and the UN COP26 (November 2021). The launch of the new EU Arctic Policy in 2021 provided an excellent framework to discuss the opportunities and needs for Arctic research and cooperation (November 2021). With the launch of the EU-PolarNet 2 call for service contracts, a novel contribution of the project, a webinar was also prepared for explaining the objectives and the application procedures. With an internal focus on EU Polar Cluster projects, the impacts of COVID-19 on the members has been discussed, allowing to share best practices and to identify priority needs.

The balance of the first year of EU-PolarNet 2 webinars is very positive, contributing to strengthening the outreach of the project, while also promoting the European activities in the Polar regions, especially through the links with the EU Polar Cluster and also benefiting of the leading role, of the European Polar Board, a key partner in the EU-PolarNet 2.

The public webinars are available online, with links provided in the report.

2 Thematic webinars dedicated to improving European cooperation

2.1 “Impact of COVID-19 on members of the EU Polar Cluster” webinar (15 January 2021)

The webinar “Impact of COVID-19 on members of the EU Polar Cluster” was organised by the [EU Polar Cluster](#) as a discussion session on the 15th of January 2021. The webinar had the participation of representatives from 20 EU Polar Cluster projects (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - “Impact of COVID-19 on members of the EU Polar Cluster” webinar.

COVID-19 has impacted nearly every sector or activity in the world. The activities of the projects of the EU Polar Cluster are no exception to this. The scientific Polar community clearly struggles with the restrictions that have severely limited the accessibility to the field and other aspects of work in research. Due to closed borders and other travel restrictions, several projects of the Polar Cluster faced unanticipated challenges in fulfilling their deliverables in their proposed timeframes, and also have had to handle associated complexities regarding funding.

Conversely, the pandemic has also presented opportunities for some projects. Several projects have found it necessary to boost their online infrastructures, benefits of which will be long-term. Overall,

EU Polar Cluster members have exhibited creativity, adaptability and resilience to continue their work during the ongoing pandemic.

Ahead of the meeting, EU Polar Cluster members were invited to provide answers to a number of questions on the issues and consequences of COVID-19 on their work, as well as best practices identified to help overcome these challenges. The webinar programme was structured in three sections: Issues, Consequences and, Best Practices (Table 1).

Table 1 - Topics and questions discussed in the “*Impact of COVID-19 on members of the EU Polar Cluster*” Webinar.

Topic	Question
Issues	In what way was the physical research infrastructure used for projects limited by local and global COVID-19 restrictions?
	Does the online infrastructure and other alternatives suffice for continuing (partial) research and communication activities in the project?
Consequences	How many and what kind of deliverables have been cancelled, postponed or otherwise affected?
	In what way have the implications of COVID-19 impacted the recruitment of project-staff?
Best practices	How do projects deal with financing of postponed activities in project?

2.2 “European Perspectives on the Arctic Science Ministerial Process” webinar (28 April 2021)

The “European Perspectives on the Arctic Science Ministerial Process” webinar was organised by the [European Polar Board \(EPB\)](#) and [EU-PolarNet 2](#) for the [3rd Arctic Science Ministerial](#), co-organised by Iceland and Japan (Figure 2). The online event took place on the 28th April 2021 and the recorded presentations were made available online on the [European Polar Board Youtube Channel](#) through the link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p4_f4uHBK2A.

Figure 2 - “European Perspectives on the Arctic Science Ministerial Process” Webinar

Since being initiated in 2016, Arctic Science Ministerial (ASM) meetings and their associated activities have provided a key, high-level coordinating platform for global research in the Arctic. This webinar aimed to explore the European perspective on the ASM process, including to underline developments since ASM2 and contributions to ASM3. The webinar explored how existing structures and entities for coordination of polar research in Europe help to facilitate the activities working towards the aims of ASM, nurturing a strong and cohesive European community for Arctic research.

The programme counted with seven invited speakers from a range of European entities working to coordinate different aspects of Arctic science and research. They have discussed how different programmes align with ASM objectives in the context of the four ASM3 Themes: Observe, Understand, Respond, and Strengthen along a session with different presentations (Table 2, Figure 3).

Table 2 - Programme of the Webinar “European Perspectives on the Arctic Science Ministerial Process”

Presentations	Speakers
Introduction	Renuka Badhe, European Polar Board
Introduction to the ASM3 process	Lindsay Arthur, Icelandic Ministry of Foreign Affairs
The upcoming EU Arctic Policy and Horizon Europe	Ana-Maria Stan, European Commission
The European Polar Research Programme	Marie-Noelle Houssais, CNRS
Coordinating and co-designing the European Research Area with EU-PolarNet 2 and the EU Polar Cluster	Nicole Biebow, Alfred Wegener Institute
ESA’s perspectives on ASM and the ESA Polar Science Cluster	Mark Drinkwater, European Space Agency
The European Polar Board and 25 years of coordination of polar research	Kirsi Latola, Thule Institute, University of Oulu
Group discussion and Q&A session	

Figure 3 - Presentation on “Coordinating and co-designing the European Research Area with EU-PolarNet 2 and the EU Polar Cluster” by Nicole Biebow.

The event had a live attendance of 38 participants corresponding to 45% of the 85 registrations. Concerning the acquaintance with the event, 49% of the attendees were informed through the EU-

PolarNet mailing list, 16% via either the Cryolist or the EPB website, 11% through the EU-PolarNet 2 website and 8% through Twitter (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Sources of information leading to participant registration in the Webinar on “European Perspectives on the Arctic Science Ministerial Process”.

Twenty nationalities were represented: 5 participants from Germany, followed by Finland, Italy, Japan and Spain with 3 participants each. The remaining countries had 1 to 2 participants.

Figure 5 - Country of origin of participants in the Webinar on “European Perspectives on the Arctic Science Ministerial Process”.

2.3 All-Atlantic “Networking from pole to pole: facilitating access for research and infrastructures” webinar (2 June 2021)

The Webinar “Networking from pole to pole: facilitating access for research and infrastructures” was co-organised by [EU-PolarNet 2](#) and [European Polar Board \(EPB\)](#) as a side event of the [All-Atlantic2021](#) conference held in Azores, Portugal (Figure 6). The event took place on the 2nd June 2021. The recorded presentations are available online in the [EU-PolarNet Youtube Channel](#) through the link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z_DdQAGqztQ.

Figure 6 - “Networking from pole to pole: facilitating access for research and infrastructures” webinar

The webinar had as main objective the discussion of how to develop a network facilitating access for the All-Atlantic partners to national research facilities and infrastructures at the poles. The event aimed also at identifying challenges, best practices, and next steps for implementing cross border access to polar research facilities and infrastructure.

The invited speakers are part of All-Atlantic partners with research activities on both poles and from the organiser institutions. Therefore, the programme had a first section with representatives from Brazil, South Africa, Canada and Europe presenting their respective Polar Research Programmes. This section was followed by a technical session where the discussion was centred on the infrastructures and logistic platforms associated with the polar research activities.

Table 3 - “Networking from pole to pole: facilitating access for research and infrastructures” programme

Presentations	Speakers
Welcome	Renuka Badhe, European Polar Board Nicole Biebow, EU-PolarNet 2
Introduction to the Polar Research Programmes of the All-Atlantic partners	
General Coordination of Science of Ocean, Antarctica and Geosciences (CGOA)	Jefferson Simões, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul
The South African Polar Research Infrastructure (SAPRI)	Marcello Vichi, University of Cape Town
Canadian polar research approach, interest and infrastructure	Alain Dupuis, Fisheries and Oceans Canada
Polar Research in Europe	Renuka Badhe, European Polar Board
Best practise examples for cross-border access to infrastructures and sharing of logistics	
Recommendations from the EU-PolarNet Infrastructure White Paper	Gonçalo Vieira, Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning, University of Lisbon
Cross-border access to Arctic icebreakers – ARICE	Veronica Willmott, Alfred Wegener Institute
Cross-border access to Arctic research stations – INTERACT	Margareta Johansson, Lund University
COMNAP Efficiency Task Force: Antarctic Peninsula	Antonio Quesada, Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación
Group Discussion on challenges, best practices, and next steps to facilitate an All-Atlantic cooperation in Polar research and sharing of infrastructures and logistics	

2.4 “How to apply for an EU PolarNet 2 Service Contract” webinar (7 July 2021)

The webinar on “How to apply for an EU PolarNet 2 Service Contract” was organised by [EU-PolarNet 2](#) and took place on 7th July 2021 (Figure 7). The recording may be found at the [EU-PolarNet Youtube Channel](#) with the link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_gdh7rqnw5c.

Figure 7 - “How to apply for an EU PolarNet 2 Service Contract” webinar

The webinar introduced the requirements for the application to the EU-PolarNet 2 Call for Services, explaining what are the EU-PolarNet 2 Service Contracts and how the participants should prepare a valid application (Table 4). The speakers were Nicole Biebow and Anneli Strobel from the Project Coordinating and Management Support Team of EU-PolarNet 2.

Table 4 - “How to apply for an EU PolarNet 2 Service Contract” programme

Presentation	Speaker
Introduction	Nicole Biebow, EU-PolarNet 2
EU-PolarNet and the European Polar Research Programme	Nicole Biebow, EU-PolarNet 2
Application procedure for EU-PolarNet 2 Service Contracts	Anneli Strobel, EU-PolarNet 2

2.5 COP26 Side event: “Polar warming, global warning” (3 November 2021)

The “Polar warming, global warning” webinar was a side event of the UN Climate Change Conference [COP26](#) held in Glasgow, United Kingdom. The webinar took place in the 3rd November 2021 and was organised by the [EU Polar Cluster](#), more specifically by the cluster members [EU-PolarNet 2](#), [SO-CHIC](#), [PROTECT](#), [TiPACCs](#) and the [European Polar Board \(EPB\)](#). It is available online on [EU Climate Action Youtube Channel](#) in the link <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5JKaoyiISHM>.

The “Polar warming, global warning” webinar included several presentations by world-leading Arctic and Antarctic climate scientists from within the Cluster projects and European research institutions. These presentations were framed in the context of the new EU Arctic Policy, the Antarctic Treaty and COP26 and had the purpose of showing that Polar Regions are experiencing faster changes than most of the regions in the world. They will further drastically change in the future, with tremendous impacts on ecosystem affecting the whole world through, for example, sea-level rise, with possible tipping points that might lead to irreversible collapse of ice sheets. Due to this fact this webinar intended to further highlight essential knowledge gaps to better understand relevant mitigation and adaptation strategies. As such, the presentations and discussions included a presentation on the support of European research policy to polar research and international science assessments, and then focussed on the impacts of polar warming such as sea level rise, ice sheet mass losses, pressure on Antarctic biodiversity, tipping points and on how polar science highlights policy needs (Table 5).

Table 5 - Programme of the Webinar “Polar warming, global warning”.

Presentations	Speakers
How does the European research policy support polar research and international assessments such as the IPCC?	Larisa Lorinczi, European Commission DG Research and Innovation
Sea level rise: what is at stake beyond 2°C?	Frank Pattyn, Université libre de Bruxelles
How much can we limit losses from the ice sheets this century?	Tamsin Edwards, King’s College London
Antarctic biodiversity under pressure: a race against time	Bruno Danis, Université libre de Bruxelles
Beyond gradual change - tipping points in Greenland and Antarctica	Ricarda Winkleman, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
Polar science highlights policy needs	Dame Jane Francis, British Antarctic Survey
Discussion	

2.6 “The new EU Arctic Policy and Research and Innovation” webinar (24 November 2021)

“The new EU Arctic Policy and Research and Innovation” webinar (Figure 8) was co-organised by the [EU Polar Cluster](#), [EU-PolarNet 2](#), and the [European Polar Board \(EPB\)](#). The event took place on the 24th November 2021 and it is available online in the [European Polar Board Youtube channel](#) in the link <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2W1V6cUDo00>.

Figure 8 - “The new EU Arctic Policy and Research an Innovation” webinar

The webinar aimed to introduce the new EU Arctic Policy to the Polar science community, to discuss the role of Research & Innovation in the new strategy and to explain how R&I projects can contribute to the Policy objectives. The webinar reflected on the contribution of EU Polar Cluster projects to better understanding changes in the Arctic, as well as on their societal impacts.

The invited speakers were representatives of the European External Action Service, the European Commission and members of the EU Polar Cluster projects, allowing to provide a comprehensive overview on the webinar issue and especially on linking Policy to Science and its stakeholders (Figure 9, Table 6). The presentations were organized in two topics: Arctic Policy and Arctic-related EU Polar Cluster projects.

Figure 9 - Invited speakers on-line during “The new EU Arctic Policy and Research an Innovation” webinar.

Table 6 - “The new EU Arctic Policy and Research and Innovation” programme

Presentations	Speakers
Introduction	Renuka Badhe, European Polar Board
Arctic Policy	
The New EU Arctic Policy	Michael Mann, EU Special Envoy for the Arctic, EEAS Raphael Goulet, Head of Unit, European Commission (DG MARE)
EU Contribution to Arctic Research	Szilvia Nemeth, Deputy Head of Unit, European Commission (DG RTD)
European Polar research coordination	Elaina Ford, EU Polar Cluster
EU Polar Cluster projects: contributing to understanding changes in the Arctic	
Permafrost thaw – time to act	Hugues Lantuit, Nunataryuk
Climate change threatens the basis of the Arctic marine food web	Sigrun Jonasdottir, ECOTIP
Envisioned Contributions of JUSTNORTH to Future EU Arctic Policy	Corine Wood-Donnelly, JustNorth
Discussion	

The webinar had an attendance of 96 participants, corresponding to 75% of the registrations. Twenty nationalities were identified. The country with highest number of participants was Belgium with 19 participants, followed by Norway and Germany with 15 and 13 participants each. The remaining countries were represented by 1 to 10 participants.

Figure 10 - Country of origin of participants in the Webinar on “The new EU Arctic Policy and Research and Innovation”.